

Effects of Mindfulness-Based Interventions on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health: A Systematic Review

Efectos de las intervenciones basadas en mindfulness sobre la salud mental de estudiantes universitarios: Una revisión sistemática

Efeitos das intervenções baseadas em mindfulness na saúde mental de estudantes de graduação: Uma revisão sistemática

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Abstract:

Objective. To synthesize the available evidence regarding the impact of mindfulness-based interventions on the mental health of undergraduate students.

Analysis. A systematic review of randomized controlled trials was performed using the terms mindfulness, mental health, undergraduate, and related expressions in the PubMed, Cochrane, and SciELO databases. Searches were conducted between January 10 and 22, 2025. From 97 identified records, 17 studies met the eligibility criteria after full-text assessment. **Results.** Most studies demonstrated positive mental health outcomes, with 81.82% reporting reductions in anxiety and stress symptoms, 69.23% showing improvements in mindfulness levels, and 50% indicating decreases in depressive symptoms. **Conclusion.** The findings suggest that mindfulness-based interventions can contribute to improving psychological well-being and may serve as a relevant approach for mental health promotion in higher education settings.

Keywords: Mindfulness-based intervention; mindfulness; mental health; undergraduate; higher education; systematic review.

Resumen

Objetivo. Sintetizar la evidencia disponible sobre el impacto de las intervenciones basadas en mindfulness en la salud mental de estudiantes universitarios. **Análisis.** Se realizó una revisión sistemática de ensayos clínicos aleatorizados utilizando los términos mindfulness, salud mental, estudiantes universitarios y expresiones relacionadas en las bases de datos PubMed, Cochrane y SciELO. La búsqueda se llevó a cabo entre el 10 y el 22 de enero de 2025. De los 97 registros identificados, 17 estudios cumplieron con los criterios de elegibilidad tras la evaluación de los

textos completos. **Resultados.** La mayoría de los estudios mostró efectos favorables sobre la salud mental, con un 81,82% reportando reducción de síntomas de ansiedad y estrés, un 69,23% evidenciando mejoras en los niveles de mindfulness y un 50% indicando disminución de síntomas depresivos. **Conclusión.** Los hallazgos sugieren que las intervenciones basadas en mindfulness pueden contribuir al bienestar psicológico y constituir una estrategia relevante para la promoción de la salud mental en el contexto de la educación superior.

Palabras clave: Intervención basada en mindfulness; mindfulness; salud mental; estudiantes universitarios; educación superior; revisión sistemática.

Resumo

Objetivo. Sintetizar as evidências disponíveis sobre o impacto das intervenções baseadas em mindfulness na saúde mental de estudantes de graduação. **Análise.** Foi realizada uma revisão sistemática de ensaios clínicos randomizados utilizando os termos mindfulness, saúde mental, graduação e expressões relacionadas nas bases de dados PubMed, Cochrane e SciELO. A busca foi conduzida entre 10 e 22 de janeiro de 2025. Dos 97 registros identificados, 17 estudos atenderam aos critérios de elegibilidade após a avaliação dos textos completos. **Resultados.** A maioria dos estudos demonstrou efeitos positivos sobre a saúde mental, sendo que 81,82% relataram redução dos sintomas de ansiedade e estresse, 69,23% evidenciaram aumento dos níveis de mindfulness e 50% indicaram diminuição dos sintomas depressivos. **Conclusão.** Os achados sugerem que as intervenções baseadas em mindfulness podem contribuir para a melhoria do bem-estar psicológico e constituir uma estratégia relevante para a promoção da saúde mental no contexto do ensino superior.

Palavras-chave: Intervenção baseada em mindfulness; mindfulness; saúde mental; estudantes universitários; educação superior; revisão sistemática.

Introduction

Mental disorders are common among college students, as the diagnosis is often made in early adolescence and persists throughout an individual's life (Auerbach et al., 2018). Moreover, late adolescence and early adulthood are marked by entry into higher education, a period of major changes in routine, as well as increased workload and responsibilities, which can directly impact stress levels and, consequently, mental health (Pedrelli et al., 2015). Financial, romantic, and relationship problems with family and peers are also among the predictors of mental health at this stage of life (Karyotaki et al., 2020).

The results from the World Mental Health International College Student Initiative revealed that 35% of students had already been diagnosed with one or more disorders, with depression (21.2% lifetime prevalence) and generalized anxiety (18.6%) being the most common disorders (Auerbach et al., 2018). In this context, the lack of adequate treatment stands out. A recent review revealed that healthcare services are rarely used by undergraduate students, both as a source of information and for treatment, and this underuse is related to multiple factors, including time, costs involved, personal and social stigma, fear of treatment, and not knowing where to seek help (Tran & Silvestri-Elmore, 2021).

Mental disorders are quite debilitating, and a lack of treatment can lead to academic, social and health problems (Nail et al., 2015; De Lijster et al., 2018; Santabárbara et al., 2020). Therefore, interventions to promote mental health are essential, with emphasis on the development of social and emotional skills for life (Patel et al., 2016), such as mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) (Jiménez-Picón et al., 2021). Some interventions, such as mental health education, physical activity, relaxation techniques and psychological therapy based on the internet and smartphones, are a priority in adult mental health self-management (Patel et al., 2016; Davies et al., 2014).

Kabat-Zinn (1990), one of the pioneers of the clinical use of mindfulness in the West, defines mindfulness as a specific form of full attention—concentrating on

the present moment intentionally and without judgment. From this perspective, [Vandenberghe and Souza \(2006, p. 36\)](#) explain that

Being present-minded means being in touch with the present and not being caught up in memories or thoughts about the future. [...] 'Intentional' means that the mindfulness practitioner makes a choice to be fully aware and strives to achieve this goal. [...] To be present-minded, the contents of thoughts and feelings are experienced as they are. They are not categorized as positive or negative. 'Nonjudgmental' means that a practitioner accepts all feelings, thoughts, and sensations as legitimate.

Increased mindfulness is intrinsically related to increased mental health and quality of life ([Kabat-Zinn, 2003](#); [Soysa & Wilcomb, 2015](#); [Aloufi et al., 2021](#)).

In this way, MBIs stand out because they use a positive, inclusive approach and can adapt to different contexts and cultures to enhance other interventions, as they act in the development of other psychological resources, such as a sense of coherence, resilience and emotional intelligence ([Généreux et al., 2020](#); [Recabarren et al., 2019](#); [Jiménez-Picón et al., 2021](#)).

Given the above, the importance of promoting mental health in the university population is evident, with the aim of improving quality of life and academic performance and building educational and healthy environments. Thus, this study aimed to systematically review and analyze randomized clinical trials (RCTs) that addressed the use of MBIs in promoting undergraduate students' health, with an emphasis on reducing symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression.

Methodology

The study review was based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 items, whose updated guidelines indicate the recommended elements for reporting systematic reviews ([Page et al.,](#)

2021). The searches for articles were carried out in three databases: PubMed, Cochrane and SciELO. The search period was between January 10 and 22, 2025. The descriptors “mindfulness” AND “mental health” AND “undergraduate” and their variations were used.

Inclusion criteria

For the systematic review, RCTs whose interventions were based on mindfulness, which included undergraduate students, assessed mental health variables (stress, anxiety, depression) postintervention and were published between 2015 and 2025 were included.

Research strategy

Two authors independently searched the databases and selected articles on the basis of the descriptors and inclusion criteria. In the Cochrane Library, 84 articles were found; in PubMed, 13 articles were found; and in SciELO, no articles were found, totaling 97 records, all in English. Duplicate records (n=11), study protocols (n= 31), those without a full-text article (n=13) and those that did not comply with the topic and/or study design required (n=25) were removed, resulting in the eligibility of 17 articles for the review.

The PRISMA flowchart (Page et al., 2021) (Figure 1) illustrates the stages followed in the selection, screening and exclusion processes.

Critical assessment

Assessments were performed by two independent reviewers. The decision to include or exclude a study was based on the assessment tool items (randomization, comparability, instruments used to measure the results and statistical analysis). If both reviewers agreed, the study was included. There was no disagreement among the reviewers.

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart showing the different phases of the systematic review

Note: The authors, on the basis of research data.

Data extraction and synthesis

The article author(s), year of publication, country, type of intervention, intervention duration, participants, variables, instruments and main results were extracted by the first author and checked for accuracy by the second author. The main findings were synthesized and tabulated in Excel spreadsheets.

Results

General characteristics of the studies

A total of 17 randomized controlled trials published between 2015 and 2024 were included in this review (Table 1). The studies were conducted across 12 countries, including Canada (n = 3), the United States (n = 3), China (n = 2), and one study each from South Korea, Malaysia, the United Kingdom, Switzerland, Brazil, Denmark, Spain, Finland, and Morocco.

Sample sizes ranged from 30 to 616 participants, totaling 2,252 university students. Most studies were conducted among university students from health-related disciplines, including nursing and medical students, although some studies involved psychology students, teacher education students, working undergraduates, students with elevated stress levels, and students with specific conditions such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). All studies were conducted among students enrolled in traditional campus-based higher education programs.

All interventions were offered to students of both sexes; however, participants were predominantly female. Fifteen of the 17 studies reported a majority of female participants, and in 11 studies women accounted for 75% or more of the sample, likely reflecting the overrepresentation of disciplines such as nursing, psychology, and teacher education. Participants were predominantly young adults enrolled in undergraduate programs, although one study also included graduate students (Galante et al., 2018).

Interventions varied considerably in format, content, delivery mode, and duration, ranging from 4 to 8 weeks. Most were based on established mindfulness approaches, including Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR), Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT), Mindfulness Skills for Students (MSS), and Mindfulness Virtual Community (MVC). Several studies evaluated adaptations of these protocols or interventions inspired by their core principles. For example, Phang et al. (2015) developed a 5-week mindfulness-based stress management program drawing on MBSR and MBCT principles, whereas Gu et al. (2018) implemented an abbreviated version of MBCT. Similarly, Mindfulness Living With Challenge (MLWC) incorporated elements of MBSR and Mindful Awareness Practices (Dai et al., 2022), while MVC, evaluated in three studies, was a web-based program inspired by MBCT (Ahmad et al., 2020; El Morr et al., 2020; Ritvo et al., 2021).

Table 1. Characteristics of the randomized controlled trials evaluating mindfulness-based

interventions among undergraduate students.

Author (year)	Country	N	Intervention	Sample
Song & Lindquist (2015)	South Korea	50	8-week Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR)	Nursing students
Phang et al. (2015)	Malaysia	75	5-week Mindfulness-Based Stress Management (MBSM)	Medical students
Falsafi (2016)	United States	90	8-week mindfulness meditation program vs yoga	Undergraduate students with anxiety/depression
Galante et al. (2018)	United Kingdom	616	8-week Mindfulness Skills for Students	University students
Gu et al. (2018)	China	54	6-week Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT)	Undergraduate students with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder.
Huberty et al. (2019)	United States	88	8-week Calm mindfulness app	Undergraduates with elevated stress levels
Recabarren et al. (2019)	Switzerland	64	8-week multidimensional stress prevention program	Healthy undergraduate students
Damião Neto et al. (2020)	Brazil	141	6-week mindfulness meditation program	Medical students
Ahmad et al. (2020)	Canada	119	8-week Mindfulness Virtual Community (MVC) vs partial MVC	Undergraduate students
El Morr et al. (2020)	Canada	160	8-week Mindfulness Virtual Community (MVC)	Undergraduate students
Ritvo et al. (2021)	Canada	154	8-week Mindfulness Virtual Community (MVC)	Undergraduate students
Juul et al. (2021)	Denmark	67	8-week Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR)	Undergraduate teacher education students
Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021)	Spain	30	6-week Mindfulness- and Compassion-Based Program	Psychology undergraduate students
Wingert et al. (2022)	United States	52	8-week Mindfulness-Based Strengths Practice	Working undergraduate students
Repo et al. (2022)	Finland	102	8-week Mindfulness Skills for Students	Health sciences students
Dai et al. (2022)	China	120	6-week Mindfulness Living With Challenge (MLWC)	Nursing students
Takhdat et al. (2024)	Morocco	70	4-week mindfulness meditation program	Nursing and medical students

Note: The authors, on the basis of research data.

Several interventions incorporated additional components beyond mindfulness practice. Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021) evaluated a mindfulness- and compassion-based program, whereas Falsafi (2016) emphasized self-compassion. Recabarren et al. (2019) assessed a multidimensional stress prevention program that integrated mindfulness techniques with cognitive-behavioral strategies, social skills training, assertiveness, and emotion regulation exercises. Wingert et al. (2022) evaluated Mindfulness-Based Strengths Practice, which combined mindfulness exercises with the identification and application of character strengths from a positive mental health perspective. Two studies applied Mindfulness Skills for Students (MSS), a program derived from MBCT and adapted for university settings (Galante et al., 2018; Repo et al., 2022).

Intervention delivery modes also varied across studies. Most programs were delivered in face-to-face group formats, with weekly sessions ranging from approximately 1 to 2.5 hours in duration. Several studies evaluated online interventions, including Mindfulness Virtual Community (MVC) and Mindfulness Living With Challenge (MLWC), whereas Takhdad et al. (2024) assessed a brief mindfulness meditation intervention adapted from MBSR in the context of emergency simulation training. The most distinct delivery format was the mindfulness meditation mobile application evaluated by Huberty et al. (2019), which required participants to engage in daily 10-minute meditation practice over an 8-week period rather than attend scheduled group sessions.

Most studies ($n = 16$) compared mindfulness-based interventions with passive control conditions, most commonly wait-list controls ($n = 10$). The exception was the study by Damião Neto et al. (2020), which employed an active control group that received educational content related to campus organization, medical training, and the medical profession. While most trials compared a single mindfulness intervention with a control condition, three studies included two active intervention arms. Ahmad et al. (2020) compared partial and full versions of MVC, Falsafi (2016) compared mindfulness and yoga, and Repo et al. (2022) compared an in-person mindfulness intervention with an online Acceptance and Commitment Therapy-based program

(Student Compass), in addition to a control group.

Table 2. Outcomes assessed, instruments, and main findings of the included studies

Author (Year)	Instruments	Main Findings
Song & Lindquist (2015)	DASS-21; MAAS	Reduced depression, anxiety, and stress; improved mindfulness.
Phang et al. (2015)	MAAS; PSS; GHQ; GSE	Reduced perceived stress and mental distress; improved mindfulness and self-efficacy.
Falsafi (2016)	BDI; HAS; SLSI; SCS-SF; CAMS-R	Reduced depression, anxiety, and stress; improved self-compassion and mindfulness.
Galante et al. (2018)	CORE-OM; WEMWBS	Reduced psychological distress; improved well-being.
Gu et al. (2018)	BAI; BDI-2; MAAS	Reduced anxiety and improved mindfulness; no significant effect on depression.
Huberty et al. (2019)	PSS; FFMQ; SCS-SF	Reduced perceived stress; improved mindfulness and self-compassion.
Recabarren et al. (2019)	MINI; Symptom Checklist; BDI-2; STAI; LSAS; OQ; WHOQOL; GSE; SOC-13; SCS-SF; MSPSS	Improved self-compassion, sense of coherence, and quality of life; reduced anxiety, pain, and interpersonal problems; no significant effects on depression, social anxiety, self-efficacy, or social support.
Damião Neto et al. (2020)	DASS-21; WHOQOL; FFMQ	No significant effects on stress, anxiety, depression, quality of life, or mindfulness.
Ahmad et al. (2020)	PHQ-9; BAI; PSS; QOLS; MDLSLSS; FFMQ	Both programs: reduced depression and perceived stress; improved quality of life and mindfulness; no significant effect on life satisfaction. Partial program: reduced anxiety.
El Morr et al. (2020)	PHQ-9; BAI; PSS; FFMQ	Reduced depression and anxiety; improved mindfulness; no significant effect on perceived stress.
Ritvo et al. (2021)	PHQ-9; BAI; PSS; FFMQ	Reduced perceived stress; no significant effects on depression, anxiety, or mindfulness.
Juul et al. (2021)	PSS; HSCL-5; WHO-5 Well-being Index; BRS; FFMQ-15	Improved well-being; reduced perceived stress, anxiety, and depression; no significant effects on resilience or mindfulness.
Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021)	PSS; GHQ; FFMQ; EQ-D; SCS-SF; AAQ-II	Reduced perceived stress and psychological distress; improved mindfulness, decentering, and self-compassion; reduced experiential avoidance.
Wingert et al. (2022)	PERMA-Profil; Workplace PERMA-Profil.	Improved overall well-being; no significant effect on work-related well-being.
Repo et al. (2022)	CORE-OM; FMI; PFHES; PSS; PR; PQOL; WEMWBS; RSM; EOOH	No significant effects on psychological distress, perceived stress, quality of life, mindfulness, psychological flexibility, recovery, resilience, self-perceived health, or well-being.
Dai et al. (2022)	DASS-21; FFMQ; MSPSS	Reduced anxiety and stress; improved mindfulness and perceived social support; no significant effect on depression.
Takhdat et al. (2024)	STAI; MAAS; CLRS	Reduced state anxiety and cognitive load.

Note. AAQ-II = Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II; BAI = Beck Anxiety Inventory; BDI-II = Beck

Depression Inventory-II; BRS = Brief Resilience Scale; CAMS-R = Cognitive and Affective Mindfulness Scale-Revised; CLRS = Cognitive Load Rating Scale; CORE-OM = Clinical Outcomes in Routine Evaluation Outcome Measure; DASS-21 = Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale-21 Items; EQ-D = Experiences Questionnaire–Decentering; EOOH = Evaluation of One's Own Health; FFMQ = Five Facets Mindfulness Questionnaire; FMI = Freiburg Mindfulness Inventory; GHQ = General Health Questionnaire; GSE = General Self-Efficacy Scale; HAS = Hamilton Anxiety Scale; HSCL-5 = Hopkins Symptom Checklist-5; LSAS = Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale; MAAS = Mindful Attention Awareness Scale; MINI = Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview; MDSLSS = Multidimensional Students' Life Satisfaction Scale; MSPSS = Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support; OQ = Outcome Questionnaire; PFHES = Psychological Flexibility for Higher Education Students; PHQ-9 = Patient Health Questionnaire-9; PQOL = Perceived Quality of Life; PR = Perceived Recovery; PSS = Perceived Stress Scale; QOLS = Quality of Life Scale; RSM = Resilience Scale Modified; SCS-SF = Self-Compassion Scale–Short Form; SLSI = Student-Life Stress Inventory; SOC-13 = Sense of Coherence Scale; STAI = State-Trait Anxiety Inventory; WEMWBS = Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale; WHOQOL = World Health Organization Quality of Life Assessment.

Mental health outcomes and intervention effects

Table 2 summarizes the outcomes assessed, measurement instruments, and main findings of the included studies. Across the 17 randomized controlled trials, a wide range of psychological outcomes were evaluated, reflecting the multidimensional nature of mental health. The most frequently assessed outcomes were mindfulness, stress, anxiety, and depression, followed by psychological well-being, quality of life, self-compassion, resilience, self-efficacy, social support, psychological distress, and sense of coherence, reflecting both pathogenic and salutogenic approaches to mental health.

Mindfulness was one of the most commonly evaluated constructs and was assessed in 13 studies using instruments such as the Five Facets of Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ) (61.5%), Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) (23.1%), Freiburg Mindfulness Inventory (FMI) (7.7%), and Cognitive and Affective Mindfulness Scale-Revised (CAMS-R) (7.7%). Positive effects on mindfulness were reported in 9 of the 13 studies that assessed this outcome (69.2%), including Song and Lindquist (2015), Phang et al. (2015), Falsafi (2016), Gu et al. (2018), Huberty et al. (2019), Ahmad et al. (2020), El Morr et al. (2020), Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021),

and Dai et al. (2022). However, some studies found no significant changes in mindfulness scores (Damião Neto et al., 2020; Ritvo et al., 2021; Juul et al., 2021; Repo et al., 2022).

Stress-related outcomes were among the most frequently assessed variables and showed the most consistent findings across studies. Eleven studies evaluated stress or perceived stress using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) the stress subscale of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21) or the Student-Life Stress Inventory (SLSI). Significant reductions in stress-related outcomes were reported in nine studies (81.8%), including Song and Lindquist (2015), Phang et al. (2015), Falsafi (2016), Huberty et al. (2019), Ahmad et al. (2020), Ritvo et al. (2021), Juul et al. (2021), Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021), and Dai et al. (2022). The only study that did not observe significant improvements in stress was Damião Neto et al. (2020). Similarly, reductions in broader measures of psychological distress were reported in three of the four studies that assessed this outcome using instruments such as the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ) and the Clinical Outcomes in Routine Evaluation Outcome Measure (CORE-OM) (Phang et al., 2015; Galante et al., 2018; Martínez-Rubio et al., 2021), suggesting benefits that extend beyond specific symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression.

Symptoms of anxiety were among the most frequently assessed clinical outcomes, being evaluated in 11 studies using a variety of instruments, including the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) (36.4%), the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21) (27.3%), the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) (18.2%), the Hamilton Anxiety Scale (HAS) (9.1%), and the Hopkins Symptom Checklist-5 (HSCL-5) (9.1%). Significant reductions in anxiety symptoms or anxiety-related measures were reported in 9 of the 11 studies (81.8%), including Song and Lindquist (2015), Falsafi (2016), Gu et al. (2018), Recabarren et al. (2019), El Morr et al. (2020), Juul et al. (2021), Dai et al. (2022), Ahmad et al., (2020) and Takhdad et al. (2024). Ahmad et al. (2020) reported mixed findings, with reductions in anxiety observed only in the partial intervention group, whereas the full program did not produce significant effects. Ritvo et al. (2021) and Damião Neto et al. (2020) did not find significant

reductions in anxiety symptoms following the intervention. Notably, Ahmad et al. (2020), El Morr et al. (2020), and Ritvo et al. (2021) evaluated versions of the Mindfulness Virtual Community (MVC) program in Canadian university students, suggesting a high degree of similarity between study populations and intervention characteristics.

Similarly, depressive symptoms were among the most frequently assessed outcomes, being evaluated in 10 studies using a variety of instruments, including the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) (27.3%), the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21) (27.3%), the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI/BDI-II) (27.3%), and the Hopkins Symptom Checklist-5 (HSCL-5) (9.1%). Significant reductions in depressive symptoms were reported in five studies (50%), namely Song and Lindquist (2015), Falsafi (2016), Ahmad et al. (2020), El Morr et al. (2020), and Juul et al. (2021). In contrast, no significant effects on depression were observed in Gu et al. (2018), Recabarren et al. (2019), Damião Neto et al. (2020), Ritvo et al. (2021), and Dai et al. (2022). These findings suggest greater variability in the effects of mindfulness-based interventions on depressive symptoms compared with the more consistent improvements observed for stress and anxiety outcomes.

Several studies also examined positive psychological resources. Self-compassion improved in studies by Falsafi (2016), Huberty et al. (2019), Recabarren et al. (2019), and Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021). Sense of coherence improved in the multidimensional stress prevention program evaluated by Recabarren et al. (2019), while self-efficacy improved in Phang et al. (2015). Improvements in psychological well-being were reported by Galante et al. (2018), Juul et al. (2021), and Wingert et al. (2022). Social support increased in Dai et al. (2022), whereas quality of life improved in Ahmad et al. (2020) and Recabarren et al. (2019). Additionally, Martínez-Rubio et al. (2021) reported improvements in decentering and reductions in experiential avoidance, suggesting enhanced psychological flexibility following the intervention.

Despite the predominance of positive findings, not all interventions produced

significant benefits. Damião Neto et al. (2020) found no significant differences between the intervention and control groups in symptoms of stress, anxiety, or depression, nor in mindfulness or quality of life. The authors suggested that the mandatory nature of participation, combined with the large-group format of the intervention, may have limited participant engagement and contributed to the absence of significant effects. Similarly, Repo et al. (2022) reported no significant effects across a broad range of outcomes, including psychological distress, mindfulness, psychological flexibility, recovery, resilience, quality of life, and well-being. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of mindfulness-based interventions may vary according to factors such as intervention format, participant characteristics, level of engagement, and contextual implementation.

Overall, the findings indicate that mindfulness-based interventions were generally associated with improvements in mental health among university students, particularly through reductions in stress, anxiety, and psychological distress, as well as increases in mindfulness, self-compassion, well-being, and other psychological resources. Evidence for depressive symptoms was less consistent, although half of the studies assessing this outcome reported significant improvements. However, the magnitude and consistency of effects varied across studies and outcomes.

Discussion

This systematic review synthesized evidence from 17 randomized controlled trials examining the effects of MBIs on the mental health of university students. Overall, the findings suggest that MBIs are associated with improvements in several dimensions of mental health, particularly stress, anxiety, mindfulness, psychological well-being, and other positive psychological resources. At the same time, the review revealed considerable heterogeneity in intervention characteristics, outcome measures, instruments, and participant profiles. This variability limited direct comparisons across studies and may partly explain the inconsistencies observed for some outcomes.

Despite the growing body of evidence, important gaps remain in the literature.

Most studies were conducted among students enrolled in traditional campus-based programs and were concentrated in North America, Europe, and China, regions that have contributed substantially to mindfulness research. The predominance of female participants across the included studies limits the generalizability of the findings. Although mindfulness-based interventions were generally associated with positive mental health outcomes, it remains unclear whether similar effects would be observed in more gender-balanced samples or among male students, who were underrepresented in most studies. Consequently, caution is warranted when generalizing these findings to male students and more gender-balanced university populations.

With respect to intervention duration, most programs were carried out over eight weeks, with weekly sessions lasting 1--2.5 hours. However, shorter interventions were equally effective, which is supported by other studies ([Carmody & Baer, 2009](#); [Strohmaier et al., 2021](#)). Thus, it is possible that more compact interventions are suitable for undergraduate students, whose needs are imminent, although they are hindered by barriers such as multiple activities and, consequently, time constraints.

Like in-person interventions, virtual interventions have been shown to be beneficial. [Huberty et al. \(2019\)](#) assessed the use of a mindfulness mobile application (app) and reported a decrease in perceived stress as well as an increase in psychological resources such as mindfulness and self-compassion. [Ahmad et al. \(2020\)](#), [El Morr et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Ritvo et al. \(2021\)](#) applied a virtual program called MVC, which had positive effects on psychological health. [Dai et al. \(2022\)](#) reported a significant reduction in stress and anxiety, as well as an increase in mindfulness, when the impact of an online program was analyzed, which is consistent with the review and meta-analysis by [Davies et al. \(2014\)](#), which suggested the effectiveness of virtual interventions in reducing symptoms related to stress and mood disorders.

Mindfulness was the most frequently investigated outcome in relation to the effects of MBIs ($n = 13$) and was associated with significant increases in 9 of the 13

studies that assessed this outcome (69.2%). These findings are relevant, given the well-established association between mindfulness and psychological health (Soysa & Wilcomb, 2015; Hofmann & Gómez, 2017; Strohmaier et al., 2021). As a psychological resource, mindfulness is thought to enhance awareness of present-moment experiences and promote more adaptive responses to psycho-emotional stress (Kabat-Zinn, 2003; Hoge et al., 2018). At the same time, reductions in stress and anxiety were observed more consistently across studies than increases in mindfulness itself. This pattern suggests that increases in mindfulness alone may not fully account for the benefits observed following MBIs, and that broader changes in psychological resources and adaptive coping processes may also play an important role. Improvements in self-compassion, sense of coherence, social support, decentering, and experiential avoidance observed in some studies support the possibility that multiple mechanisms contribute to the promotion of mental health and well-being among university students.

There is abundant evidence for the protective effect that increased mindfulness has on stress symptoms. In the present study, perceived stress was one of the most studied variables and showed the most consistent positive findings across the included studies, since the vast majority of studies reported significant reductions in these symptoms postintervention. These findings are consistent with those of previous studies that assessed the effects of MBI in university populations and other groups (Aloufi et al., 2021; Van Agteren et al., 2021) and are significant because of the implications that stress has on the development of psychological disorders (Shapiro et al., 2019; Homayuni, 2023).

Symptoms of depression appear to be less consistently responsive to mindfulness interventions than stress and anxiety outcomes, with significant reductions reported in only half of the studies that assessed this variable. Since conventional treatments are also limited in remitting symptoms, these data do not disqualify the effects of mindfulness for people with depressive disorders but rather attribute an important role to MBI as a complementary strategy to already established treatments. According to Goyal et al. (2014), although small, the effect

of mindfulness meditation on people with symptoms of anxiety and depression is similar to the effect of antidepressant medications, with the benefit of no side effects.

A reduction in symptoms of anxiety was predominant in the studies analyzed. Previous reviews have demonstrated the effectiveness of MBI in reducing the severity of depression and symptoms of anxiety and have compared their performance to that of CBT (Hofmann & Gómez, 2017; Li et al., 2021). Although the mechanisms of action are rarely studied, the literature asserts that the impact of MBI may be associated with emotional and cognitive reactivity, increased mindfulness, and decreased rumination and concern (Gu et al., 2015). This mechanism reveals the reason why interventions are potentially beneficial in anxious patients, since they act on the predominant symptoms of anxiety disorders.

Mental health dimensions such as well-being and distress have been incorporated into few studies, but there is evidence that they are positively impacted by the MBI. However, few studies have addressed variables such as psychological resources, which can help explain the mechanisms of action that act to increase mental health and well-being (Lindström & Eriksson, 2010). The small number of studies also limits the inference of effectiveness regarding these variables.

Mindfulness, resilience, self-compassion, and self-efficacy are considered health assets that positively influence the perception of mental health, reducing signs of stress, anxiety, and depression (Asensio-Martínez et al., 2019; Soysa & Wilcomb, 2015). Studies aimed at promoting mental health have increasingly focused on factors and processes that can help individuals react better when faced with adverse situations. Resilience, for example, is highlighted as an important resource in the search for sustainable psychological well-being (Ungar & Theron, 2020). Likewise, an increased sense of coherence is a predictor of better mental health (Penachiotti et al., 2023).

The results of this review are in line with the results reported by other studies and reviews that assessed the effects of the MBI on mental health. A systematic review and meta-analysis revealed evidence that MBIs are among the most effective

psychological interventions for promoting mental well-being in clinical and nonclinical populations (Van Agteren et al., 2021). According to Aloufi et al. (2021), the MBI stands out as a mental health strategy within universities. The review presented relevant results for reducing stress, anxiety and depression experienced by nursing students, although it warns that the studies still lack larger samples and methodological rigor.

In relation to the limitations of this study, searches were conducted in only three databases that, although important, may not have captured all relevant studies on the topic. In addition, all included studies were conducted among students enrolled in traditional campus-based higher education programs. Given the rapid expansion of distance education worldwide, future research should investigate whether similar benefits can be achieved among students enrolled in fully online degree programs.

Another limitation concerns the characteristics of the study samples. Participants were predominantly female, and most studies reported a substantial overrepresentation of women, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to more gender-balanced university populations. In addition, considerable variability was observed across samples, including healthy students, students with elevated stress levels, volunteers, and nonvolunteers. Most studies were also conducted in high-income countries, particularly in North America and Europe, which may limit the applicability of the findings to low- and middle-income settings, where educational, cultural, and mental health support contexts may differ substantially.

Although only randomized controlled trials were included, the interventions analyzed were highly heterogeneous, varying in content, delivery mode, duration, session frequency, and methodological characteristics. This heterogeneity limited direct comparisons across studies and may have contributed to the variability observed in outcomes. Additionally, most studies employed passive control conditions, particularly wait-list controls, which may have led to an overestimation of intervention effects and limited comparisons with other active mental health

promotion strategies. Finally, the relatively short follow-up periods adopted in most studies restrict conclusions regarding the long-term sustainability of intervention effects. Future studies should incorporate active comparison groups and longer follow-up assessments to strengthen the evidence base.

Overall, the evidence synthesized in this review suggests that mindfulness-based interventions constitute a promising strategy for promoting mental health among university students. The most consistent benefits were observed for stress reduction, anxiety management, and the enhancement of mindfulness and positive psychological resources. Although findings for depression and some secondary outcomes were less consistent, the overall pattern of evidence supports the integration of mindfulness-based approaches into university mental health promotion initiatives. Future research should prioritize more diverse student populations, active comparison groups, longer follow-up periods, and greater attention to salutogenic outcomes and mechanisms of change.

Conclusion

The evidence suggests a positive effect of MBI on undergraduate students' mental health, with emphasis on increased mindfulness and reduced symptoms related to stress and anxiety. A reduction in symptoms of depression, although less prominent, is important, since even therapeutic and/or drug treatment encounters resistance in mitigating the clinical symptoms of the disorder. In addition, interventions with different characteristics, in person or online, of longer or shorter duration had similar and positive results. Thus, MBIs present themselves as potentially beneficial strategies for promoting the mental health of undergraduate students.

There is still a lack of literature on the effects of MBIs on psychological resources that support or enhance mental health, especially when individuals are exposed to acute or ongoing stress. It is therefore suggested that the scope of studies be expanded to better understand the range of variables involved in psychological health, with a view to strengthening health assets and, consequently, more assertive mental health interventions. Furthermore, studies that include other

populations, such as men and distance learning students, and longitudinal studies that can provide more evidence of the long-term effects of MBIs are recommended.

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